

STRUCTURAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Annotation. In the context of globalization, achieving sustainable growth is linked to the structural policy of the state. The structural policy of the state is primarily aimed at changing the ratio of economic sectors. Based on this, this paper examines the theoretical foundations of the structural transformation of the national economy.

Keywords: national economy, economic structure, diversification, structural policy, drivers of structural policy. innovations, technologies.

The categorical apparatus of the study of the financial potential of the structural transformation of the national economy. The theory of the formation and use of the financial potential of the structural transformation of the national economy includes the identification of its economic essence and sources, the interaction of the national financial potential with other elements of the potential of the structural transformation of the economy, as well as the study of the impact of the financial potential of the structural transformation of the national economy on its macroeconomic state.

The structural transformation of the national economy is a process of changes in the proportions between industries and industries under the influence of widespread use of innovations and modern technologies, accompanied by the expansion of functioning and the emergence of new markets.

The main drivers of structural transformation are the increment of scientific and technical knowledge that allows the creation and use of new materials and high-tech equipment, as well as the development of digital technologies that provide extensive automation of technological processes.

The manifestations of the structural transformation of the national economy include the emergence of new goods and services that meet the needs of businesses and households. This includes the development of new technologies that reduce production costs and the broad international cooperation that takes place in the production sector. Modern communication systems and the growth of online commerce are also important factors in this transformation.

It is important to note that the development of all these phenomena is ensured by the increment of knowledge, the creation of intelligent products and their accelerated commercialization.

The economic result of the structural transformation of the national economy is an increase in both the volume and growth rates of value added created by economic entities. Moreover, the growth of added value can be ensured both by increasing consumption in the domestic economy and by exporting goods, technologies and services.

The structural transformation of the national economy can take place both under the influence of market forces and as a result of targeted actions by regulatory authorities. In the first case, the main role in the transformation processes is played by national business structures and research centers. The latter can carry out their activities, including at the expense of state funding. This type of structural transformation is typical for the United States and European countries.

The transformation of the national economy as a result of targeted actions by regulatory authorities has been historically observed in countries seeking to bridge the technological gap with developed countries in a relatively short period of time. In this process, the role of regulatory authorities has been significant, manifested through the development and implementation of government programs aimed at accelerating technological advancement and supporting export-oriented industries. This type of structural transformation has been implemented in different historical contexts in countries such as Japan, South Korea, Singapore, and Taiwan, among others.

The main objectives of the structural transformation of the national economy are: ensuring sustained growth of GDP, increasing the share of high-tech industries in the economy, expanding exports of high-tech products, maintaining stable domestic demand, and ensuring high levels of innovation among businesses.

The achievement of these goals of the structural transformation of the national economy is ensured by solving the following tasks: ensuring relative macroeconomic stability, expressed in the stability of the national currency and low rates of price dynamics; budget support for the high-tech sector; providing tax incentives to high-tech companies; state guarantees on loans to companies exporting high-tech products, as well as on loans used for the purchase, including abroad, patents and high-tech equipment.

The results of the structural transformation of the national economy are: economic diversification, increased innovative activity of business structures in the national and global markets, increased output of high-tech products, increased cash flows to the budget system, reduced price dynamics, stabilization of the national currency, maintaining stable aggregate effective demand in the national economy.

An increase in financial potential makes it possible to generate additional financial sources of resources that ensure an increase in other elements of economic potential. In turn, the effective use of other potentials means the creation of additional sources of added value. Its increase means an increase in financial potential.

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